

Uncovering Intersections of Health and E-literacy and Morality Among Adults with Hypertension

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Preferred Presentation Type: ePoster presentation

Topic: Health Literacy

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Objectives: To assess how health and e-literacy influence engagement and mortality among socioeconomically disadvantaged and older adults with hypertension, in order to form recommendations for research on the development of equitable, patient-centered digital health interventions for cardiovascular care.

Background: Despite knowing that e-health literacy and participation is hindered by older age and socioeconomic status, few studies have assessed customized digital literacy interventions for such high-risk groups. Thus, studying how health/digital literacy affects the engagement and outcomes of vulnerable cardiovascular patients is imperative to develop equitable patient-centered digital health interventions.

Methods: In order to analyze the literature, we generated 511 preliminary articles by inputting the following search terms into the Web of Science Core Collection: *chronic hypertension, mortality, patient-physician relationship*. Subsequently, we eliminated and excluded articles that addressed our topic within the context of kidney diseases, HIV, and other non relevant chronic diseases. Moreover, we focused on specifically article or review articles that were published within the year of 2024 in order to streamline our specificity. Of the articles that remained, we exported the bibliometric data of the 100 most cited options into Google Sheets for analysis.

Results: After analyzing the 17 most frequently referenced keywords in the articles, the two primary focuses in the literature that emerged: hypertension/blood pressure elevation and preventable risk factor. The first category included terms such as *global epidemic* (7 references), *personalized medicine* (5 references), and *public health challenge* (5 references). The second category included terms such as *epidemiology trends* (5 references), *pathophysical mechanisms* (5 references), and *diagnosis* (5 references).

Conclusions: Scientists could expand the literature by rigorously examining the pre-existing topics in the two categories. Additionally, they could explore topics that place emphasis on customized care and utilizing patient-centered digital health interventions to enhance mortality rates.

Keyword 1: Chronic Hypertension

Keyword 2: Medical Literacy

Keyword 3: Patient-physician relationship

Keyword 4: Morality

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